

CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Education is the foundation for the development of a nation and the role of teachers is vital. Continuous Professional Development (CPD) plays a crucial role in enhancing teachers' competencies, instructional practices, and overall professional growth to meet the educational challenges in the rapidly changing world. The present study aimed to examine the level of CPD among secondary school teachers adopting a Descriptive Research Design. Data was collected from 100 Government secondary school teachers in Rangeilunda Block of Ganjam District, Odisha by using Teacher's Professional Development Scale. The findings revealed that gender, subject stream, and teaching experience did not significantly influence the overall professional development levels of secondary school teachers. However, female teachers and science stream teachers scored higher than their counterparts in the dimension of Commitment and Accountability. The results suggest that CPD opportunities are generally inclusive and equally accessible to teachers irrespective of their demographic variables. The study highlights the importance of strengthening targeted CPD initiatives, regular monitoring, and collaborative support systems to enhance teachers' professional growth and improve the quality of secondary education.

Keywords: *Continuous Professional Development, Secondary School Teachers*

Introduction

Education is important for the growth of individuals, society, and the whole country. In this, the teacher is the center, and good teaching plays a big role in how well students learn. Beyond sharing knowledge, teachers influence students in many ways by offering guidance, support, and encouragement. As NCF 2005 has described Secondary school period

is a time of intense physical change and formation of identity. It is also a period of intense vibrancy and energy. The ability for abstract reasoning and logical thinking emerges, allowing children the possibility of deep engagement with both understanding and generating knowledge about their future. An understanding of the self in relation with society also emerges in this period. At the same time, teachers are taking on new responsibilities. These shifts show how the role of a teacher is becoming more complex and important than ever before.

“A teacher can never truly teach unless he still learning himself. A lamp cannot light another lamp unless it continues to burn its own flame.” (Rabindranath Tagore). This idea reinforce to ongoing professional development of teachers in the education system. As Darling-Hammond (2006) noted, “the quality of an education system cannot exceed the quality of its teachers,” underscoring the need for well-prepared and continuously supported educators. So one way to improve their skills and their competency is through Continuous Professional Development (CPD), which helps them stay updated, think critically about their teaching, and respond better to students’ needs.

CPD helped in improving instructional strategies, supporting career mobility, and keeping teachers updated with subject knowledge and pedagogical innovations. Teachers also reported CPD as beneficial for goal setting, student engagement, and motivation. (Banik and Saha, 2023). Ambon et al. (2024) reviewed that CPD significantly improves teachers’ pedagogical skills, classroom problem-solving abilities, and reflective practices.

Ngendahayo et al. (2023) analysed in Public Secondary Schools in Rwanda of Karongi District indicated a moderate but significant positive correlation between CPD participation and student achievement. This impacted improvements in pedagogical planning, teaching methodology, subject content, and classroom management by supporting teachers in preparing lesson plans, using evaluation tools, and collaborating with peers. Haloj and Kharbiryumbai (2024) concluded that the overall professional development level of secondary school teachers in Kamrup region was above average but male teachers were found to have higher professional development scores than female teachers. Singh et al. (2024) found no significant difference in students’ perception of CPD whether their teachers had 0–5 or 5–10 years of experience. Study by Behera and Behera (2021) have made note that Arts teachers demonstrated higher teaching efficiency and accountability compared to science teachers after undergoing a training program.

NEP 2020 has introduced structured, competency based, technology integrated CPD, also mandated 50 hours of annual training for all teachers and institutional monitoring (Sahoo, 2024). While policy focused and theoretical literature recognises the importance and impacts of CPD, there is a lack of empirical, data driven comprehensive studies. So, the following research questions were formulated to guide this study.

- Does the Continuous Professional Development of secondary school teachers differ in relation to their gender, stream or years of experiences?

Operational Definition of Key Terms

- **Continuous Professional Development:** “CPD is a planned, continuous and lifelong process whereby teachers try to develop their personal and professional qualities, and to improve their knowledge, skills and practice, leading to their empowerment, the improvement of their agency and the development of their organization and their pupils.” Padwad and Dixit (2011)
- **Secondary School Teacher:** A secondary school teacher in India is an educational professional responsible for teaching students in classes 9 and 10

Objectives of the Study

1. To compare the professional development of the secondary school teachers (i.e. dimension-wise and total) with respect to gender i.e., Male and Female.
2. To compare the Professional development of secondary school teachers (i.e. dimension-wise and total) in terms of their streams i.e., Arts and Science.
3. To compare the professional development of school teachers (i.e. dimension-wise and total) in terms of their working experience.

Hypotheses of the Study

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean professional development scores (i.e. dimension-wise and total) of male and female secondary school teachers.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Continuous Professional Development (i.e. dimension-wise and total) in relation to their subject stream (i.e. Arts and Science).

H03: There is no significant difference in the mean professional development scores (i.e. dimension-wise and total) in relation to their experience. (Less than and more than 10 years).

Methodology

- **Method:** To fulfill the objectives a Descriptive research design was employed by the researcher to gather precise information about the phenomenon, as well as to draw logical conclusions.
- **Population and Sample:** The study was limited to only on the government secondary school teachers under Rangeilunda Block of Ganjam District. The sample for present study has been limited 100 teachers drawn from 15 secondary schools by applying stratified random sampling method.
- **Tools for Data Collection:** Teacher’s Professional Development scale by Dr. Yodida Bhutia was used by the investigator for collecting relevant data. It is a five point rating scale [ranging from “Always” to “Never”] includes 64 items on 5 dimensions i.e. Knowledge, Competencies in Teaching ,Commitment and Accountability of Teachers ,Leadership and Personal Effectiveness, Self-upgrading and Extended Reading.

Teachers’ Professional Development Scale

- **Procedure of Data Collection:** The investigator personally visited the sample institutions with prior permission from the head of each institution; the tool was administered individually to all the selected teachers in the respective schools.
- **Statistical Techniques Used:** The collected data were analysed using both descriptive statistics (Mean and Standard Deviation) and inferential statistical methods (t-test).

• Result and Discussion

➤ The first objective of the study was to examine and compare the professional development between male and female secondary school teachers in Rangeilunda Block. The scores obtained from the participants were organized gender-wise in a frequency distribution table. t-test was applied at both the 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance. The findings of the analysis are presented in Table-1.

Table-1: Compare between Male and Female secondary school teachers with respect to professional Development (dimension-wise and total).

Sl. No.	Dimension of Professional Development	Female (N=60)		Male (N=40)		t-value	Tabulated value (0.05)
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1	Knowledge	42.13	4.97	42.78	4.92	0.59	1.984
2	Competencies in Teaching	44.63	3.88	43.48	4.39	1.35	1.984
3	Commitment and Accountability	46.98	4.73	44.13	5.49	2.69**	1.984* 2.626**
4	Leadership and Personal Effectiveness	56.5	5.62	55.83	6.02	0.56	1.984
5	Self-upgrading and Extended Reading	39.2	4.7	38.55	5.12	0.64	1.984
6	Total	229.45	18.14	224.75	18.96	1.24	1.984

* $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$

Bar Diagram showing Mean Scores of Five Dimensions of Professional Development and total for Male and Female Secondary School Teachers

Table-1 shows that gender does not significantly influence the overall professional development of secondary school teachers in the sampled group. Therefore the null hypothesis is retained at 0.05 level of significance ($t = 1.24$, $p > 0.05$). However

in the dimension of Commitment and Accountability female teachers (M= 46.98) are differ significantly from male teachers (M= 44.13) ($t = 2.69, p < 0.01$).

➤ The second objective of the study was aimed to compare the professional development levels of teachers from the Arts stream and those from the Science stream. The findings of the analysis are presented in Table-2.

Table-2: Compare between the Arts and Science Secondary School Teachers with respect to Professional Development (dimension-wise and total)

Sl. No.	Dimension of Professional Development	Science stream (N=37)		Arts stream (N=63)		t-value	Tabulated value (0.05)
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
		1	Knowledge	41.68	5.36		
2	Competencies in Teaching	44.05	4.33	44.24	4.1	0.22	1.984
3	Commitment and Accountability	47.35	4.5	44.95	5.43	2.38*	1.984
4	Leadership and Personal Effectiveness	56.68	5.75	55.97	5.8	0.60	1.984
5	Self-upgrading and Extended Reading	39.05	4.81	38.87	4.92	0.18	1.984
6	Total	228.81	19.17	226.84	18.43	1.142	1.984

* $p < 0.05$

Bar Diagram showing Mean Scores of Five Dimensions of Professional Development and total for Science and Arts Stream Secondary School Teachers

Science teachers scored slightly higher in the overall professional development ($M = 228.81$) compared to Arts teachers ($M = 226.84$) but the observed difference is not statistically significant between the two groups ($t = 1.142, p > 0.05$). The only exception was in the dimension of commitment and accountability, where Science teachers scored significantly higher than their counterparts ($t = 2.38, p < 0.05$).

➤ Another important variable considered in relation to professional development was the teaching experience of secondary school teachers. The third objective of the study was to examine whether the number of years of service had any influence on the professional development of teachers working in Rangeilunda Block. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 3, which provides a comparative summary of the professional development scores of teachers based on their years of experience.

Table-3: Compare between the Means of less experienced and more experienced secondary school teachers with respect to professional development (Dimension-wise and total)

Sl. No.	Dimension of Professional Development	Less Experienced (N= 32)		More Experienced (N= 68)		t-value	Tabulated value (0.05)
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1	Knowledge	43.03	4.49	42.09	5.14	0.93	1.984
2	Competencies in Teaching	54.19	3.81	52.16	4.27	1.72	1.984
3	Commitment and Accountability	46.91	4.21	45.39	5.58	1.52	1.984
4	Leadership and Personal Effectiveness	57.62	4.65	55.57	6.16	1.86	1.984
5	Self-upgrading and Extended Reading	39.41	4.32	38.72	5.10	0.70	1.984
6	Total	231.25	17.1	224.98	19.26	1.64	1.984

Bar Diagram showing Mean Scores of Five Dimensions of Professional Development and total for less and more experienced Secondary School Teachers

In view of the statistical analysis (Table- 3), the null hypothesis - that there is no significant difference in the mean professional development scores between teachers with less than 10 years and those with more than 10 years of teaching experience is retained ($t = 1.64, p > 0.05$). A dimension wise analysis shows that in all five dimensions - Knowledge, Competencies in Teaching, Commitment and Accountability, Leadership and Personal Effectiveness, and Self-upgrading and Extended Reading - the t-values remained below the critical value. This suggests that professional development levels across these dimensions are not significantly different between less experienced and more experienced teachers.

Educational Implications

Research holds little value unless its findings contribute to practical applications with meaningful impact. The results of the present study offer several educational implications:

- The study shows CPD programmes are inclusive and equitable, as neither gender nor subject stream or years of experience significantly affects teachers' professional development.
- A significant difference was observed in the area of Commitment and Accountability, with female and Science teachers outperforming their counterparts, respectively. This highlighting the need for targeted interventions- such as training, mentoring, or workshops to strengthen commitment and accountability, particularly among male and Arts stream teachers.
- The Ministry of Education and educational bodies should collaborate with universities, teacher institutes, schools, parents, and communities to strengthen CPD for secondary teachers.
- Regular monitoring, proper evaluation, and follow-up are vital to maintain the usefulness and quality of CPD programmes.
- Secondary school teachers should engage more actively with other human resources- such as educational experts, mentors, colleagues, community members, and students to enhance and support their professional growth and leadership capabilities.

Conclusion

The present study explored the nature and extent of continuous professional development (CPD) among secondary school teachers, with attention to five dimensions. The findings reflect positively on the professional climate of secondary education. Gender, subject stream and experience were not significant determinants in overall CPD levels however, slight variations were observed in specific areas such as commitment and

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accountability, where female and science stream teachers exhibited higher levels of accountability than their counterparts.

The study underscores the importance of designing CPD programs that are inclusive, need-based, and embedded within the ongoing educational practices of schools. Strong collaboration among stakeholders- teachers, school heads, policy makers, and training institutions- is essential for sustaining and enhancing the professional growth of teachers to improve the quality of teaching and learning and to promote quality education in secondary schools through targeted and sustainable professional development strategies.

Bibliography

- Ambon, J., Alias, B. S., Komariah, A., & Mansor, A. N. (2024). *The impact of continuous professional development on teaching quality: A systematic review. International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education, 13(6)*, 3838–3847. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v13i6.30427>
- Banik, S., & Saha, A. (2023). *Importance of continuous professional development (CPD) program in teaching profession. International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, 11(3)*, 278–285. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18906.88004>
- Behera, L., & Behera, S. (2021). *Teaching efficiency and accountability of secondary school teachers exposed to Samarthya Programme of Odisha. Shodh Sanchar Bulletin, 11(42)*, 177–182.
- Bhutia, Y. (2014). *Manual for Teacher's professional Development Scale*. Agra: N.P.C.
- Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development. (2021). *What is continuing professional development (CPD)?* <https://www.cipd.org/uk/knowledge/cpd/what-is-cpd/>
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2006). *Powerful Teacher Education*. Jossey-Bass.
- Government of India(1966). *Education and National Development: Report of the Education Commission 1964–66 (Kothari Commission)*. Ministry of Education.
- Haloi, M., & Kharbirymbai, B. (2024). *Professional development of secondary school teachers with special reference to the Kamrup district of Assam. Tuijin Jishu / Journal of Propulsion Technology, 45(1)*, 63–67.
- Ministry of Education. (2023). *National Curriculum Framework for School Education (NCFSE) 2023*. Government of India. https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/NCF-SE_2023_English.pdf
- Ministry of Human Resource Development. (2020). *National education policy 2020*. Government of India. https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf
- National Council of Educational Research and Training. (2005). *National Curriculum Framework 2005*. NCERT. <https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/nc-framework/nf2005-english.pdf>
- Ngendahayo, J. B., Mukulira, O., & Mugo, L. (2023). *Influence of continuous professional development for secondary school teachers on academic performance in public secondary schools in Rwanda: A case of Karongi District. Journal of Education, 6(2)*, 22–34. <https://doi.org/10.53819/81018102t3094>
- Padwad, A., & Dixit, K. (2011). *Continuing professional development: An annotated bibliography*. British Council India.
- Patro, P. R. K. (2020). *Professional development and leadership behaviour of teachers of higher education in Odisha*. Doctoral Thesis, Education, Berhampur University.
- Sahoo, U. R. (2024). *Envisioning continuous professional development of teachers through National Educational Policy (NEP) 2020. International Journal for Research Trends and Innovation, 9(1)*, 783–786. <https://www.ijrti.org/papers/IJRTI2401117>.

Singh, R., Kaushik, V., Chopra, R., & Gurjar, B. R. (2024). A study on the attitude of the secondary level teachers towards continuous professional development. International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering, Technology and Science, 6(4), 3687–3691.

UNESCO. (2017). Education for Sustainable Development Goals: Learning Objectives.